

Press Release

New partnership announcement: Ministry of Health, Republic of Türkiye, joins TRUMPET project through EU Hop On initiative

The TRUMPET project is thrilled to announce the inclusion of a new partner, the **Ministry of Health of the Republic of Türkiye**, thanks to the EU's innovative Hop On initiative. This strategic collaboration marks a significant milestone in our mission to advance the integration of Federated Learning (FL) in healthcare, leveraging real-world data to drive groundbreaking research and patient care improvements.

About the Ministry of Health, Republic of Türkiye

The Ministry of Health (MOH) of the Republic of Türkiye is a leading authority overseeing more than 2,000 hospitals and 8,000 health centers. Renowned for its comprehensive healthcare services, the MOH is at the forefront of health promotion, informatics, and research in Türkiye. The **General Directorate of Health Information Systems**, a critical department within the MOH, spearheads several advanced health informatics initiatives, such as globally awarded e-Nabız EHR&PHR system, the Public Health Management System (HSYS), and the Central Physician Appointment System (MHRIS). These initiatives are pivotal in enhancing patient care and operational efficiency across Türkiye's healthcare landscape. The MOH has also taken on roles as both a coordinator and partner in many EU-funded PCP and R&D projects, such as ProEmpower, InCareHeart, Procure4Health, and Stamina.

What is the Hop On opportunity by the EU?

The Hop On initiative by the European Union is designed to foster inclusivity and collaboration within European research projects. This program allows new partners from widening countries to join existing consortia, enriching projects with diverse perspectives and expertise. By enabling additional partners to 'hop on' to ongoing projects, the initiative aims to strengthen the European Research Area by promoting balanced participation and broadening the scope and impact of research activities.

The new collaboration: enhancing TRUMPET's mission

With the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Türkiye joining the TRUMPET project, partners are poised to leverage their extensive expertise and resources in healthcare informatics. Their role as a data owner and use case validator will be instrumental in advancing our research on privacy-enhancing methods for Federated Learning. This collaboration will also bolster our efforts to support AI-powered studies with high privacy standards, ensuring robust data protection and efficiency in virtual clinical cancer research.

For more information about the TRUMPET project and our new partnership, please visit our website www.trumpetproject.eu

The TRUMPET project, funded by the European Commission, aims to revolutionize healthcare through the application of Artificial Intelligence and Federated Learning techniques. With a consortium of 10 internationally renowned partners, TRUMPET focuses on developing innovative solutions to improve Federated Learning adoption in Healthcare while ensuring data privacy and security.